
MICROBIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SACHET DRINKING WATER MARKETED AT TWO SITES IN ALIERO, KEBBI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Sachet drinking water, often called as 'pure water' is generally accepted safe for consumption. Ten brands of sachet water are mainly marketed at Kebbi State University of Science & Technology (KSUST) campus and Onion Market of Aliero (AOM). Seven of these are NAFDAC registered. Bacteriological analysis of 50 samples of each of the sachet drinking water samples was carried out to determine the potability of the sampled water. Standard conventional methods were employed for the detection of coliforms (viable count, presumptive coliform count by multiple tube method and confirm coliforms count) and other bacteria. Biochemical analysis as well as microscopic examination was performed for sediments and other debris and/or bacteria, protozoa and other fungal hyphae. Bacteriological analysis of the samples from both sites revealed the presence of pathogens (log 10cfu/ml) viz. *Shigella* spp. (3.41, 3.31), *Salmonella* spp. (2.10, 2.05), *Staphylococcus aureus* (5.04, 5.09), *Streptococcus* spp. (4.76, 4.80), *Bacillus* spp. (5.12, 5.10), *E. coli* (2.0, 1.93) and Yeasts (3.13, 4.00). Most of the sachet water brands fell below WHO drinking water standards and are therefore, of doubtful quality. Out of the ten brand samples tested, four samples showed the presence of contamination in the form of high number of coliforms and occurrence of intestinal pathogens. This indicates that the 'pure water' available in the University campus and Onion market are unfit for human consumption due to their inability to meet up with NAFDAC (2010) and WHO (2011) standard. Efforts need to be intensified in the monitoring of activities in this rapidly expanding industry with a view to raising standards.

KEYWORDS: Sachet water, microbiological quality, drinking water, bacteriological analysis

INTRODUCTION

Water is one of the most essential commodities for the survival of all lives. It is abundant in nature and occupies about 70% of the earth's crust. It is also the biological medium on earth and is the only common substance that exists in nature in all three physical state of matter: solid, liquid and gas. It is the most universally used solvent and common route of transmission of diseases (Botkin and Keller, 1998).

The demand for safe drinking water in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized, considering the inability of the governments to provide adequate pipe borne water to the populace. Well-packaged water in bottles or food grade polyethylene sachets designed for food processing stands is a ready alternative for the growing population of over 140,000,000 people. However, safe drinking water is very scarce. The ever-increasing demand of readily available water has led to the concept of sachet /pure water. It's a general perception that packaged water is safe for consumption. Sachet water in Nigeria is popularly known as 'pure water', normally sold at the rate of five naira/sachet. Potable water is any packaged water that has been processed, sealed and released into the market under sealed food grade material or other appropriate containers for human consumption (FDA, 2002). In view of the above, this feasibility relates to the production and packaging of purified water to World Health Organization (WHO) and National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) standard requirements for human consumptions. Continuous increase in the sale and indiscriminate consumption of packaged drinking waters in Nigeria is of public health significance. Most of the sachet water brands fell below WHO drinking water standards and are therefore of doubtful quality. Efforts need to be intensified in the monitoring of activities in this rapidly expanding industry with a view to raising standards.

Sachet water like any other food product must be processed and packaged under aseptic conditions free from every possible source of contamination. The potability of this water is found uncertain being collected from almost every available water source ranging from rainwater to tanker-borne water most of which are rusty and unwashed (Dibua *et al.* 2007). Adherence to production and analytical standards are doubtful as most of the factories are observed to lack the appropriate technology for achieving these standards. The standards of hygiene in the various stages of production of bottled and sachet water vary among various manufacturers. While some employ sophisticated techniques such as ozonization and reverse osmosis, most use ordinary boiling of well water sources and exclusion of particles by use of unsterilized filtration materials. However, contaminant may get introduced during collection, packaging and/or consumer handling (Warburton and Austin, 1997).

Several studies on the microbial quality of bottled and sachet water have reported violations of international quality standards. The most widely used indicator for microbial water contaminant is the coliforms group of micro-organisms. Coliforms are used as indicator of water contamination because many of them inhabit the intestinal tract of human and other animals in large number, thus, their presence in water indicates fecal contamination. Coliforms are gram positive, facultative aerobe, non-spore former, rod shaped bacteria that ferment lactose with gas formation within 24h at 35°C (Wiesenberger, 2004).

In a Canadian study, screening of bottled water for indicator bacteria revealed that 3.7% of the samples had total coliforms and 23.3% of the 3460 samples had more than 100 colonies of heterotrophic bacteria per ml of sample (Warburton *et al.*, 1998). A similar study of brands of bottled water in Trinidad showed that 18 out of the 344 samples checked revealed the presence of total coliforms while five of the samples had *Escherichia coli* and colonies of *Enterococcus faecalis* were occasionally detected in the samples (Bharath *et al.*, 2003). The quality monitoring of sachet water in Nigeria have been documented (Adekunle *et al.*, 2004; Onifade *et al.*, 2008; Dada, 2009). However, there is little information in scientific literatures on the quality of the many brands of bottled water produced and marketed by local and multinational companies. Water borne diseases continue to be one of the major health problems especially in developing nations. The high prevalence of diseases such as diarrhoea, typhoid fever, cholera and bacillary dysentery among the populace has been traced to the consumption of unsafe water and unhygienic drinking water production practices (Mead *et al.*, 1999).

Fujikawa *et al.* (1997), have reported mineral water contamination in some imported and domestic brands of bottled water in Tokyo, Japan. In another study, Gentili and Belli (1976) reported acceleration and multiplying process in waters bottled in PVC containers than those kept in glass containers. In a study of dual contamination of bottled water (*Campylobacter jejuni* and biodegradable organic matter), the survival of pathogen for relatively longer period was reported by Tatchou-Nyamsi-Konig (2007).

Drinking water standard in the United State are specified under the Safe Drinking Water Act which provides a framework for the development of drinking water standards in many other nations also.. Minimum standards are generally accepted for the coliforms bacteria. Several brands of bottled and sachet water are vended to the public. An understanding of their microbiological quality and safety are, therefore, imperative (Drinking Water Research Foundation, 2004).

It is in line with the mentioned criterions of NAFDAC and WHO that the present work was carried out to determine the microbial standards of locally produced sachet water with resultant safety and potability indices. The study aims to provide information about the safety of packaged drinking water marketed in selected areas of KSUST and AOM, Aliero, Nigeria by determining the microbiological quality of several of the brands. This will give an understanding of the extent to which the products meet the standards and recommendations of the WHO and NAFDAC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples: The water samples used for this work were sachet or packaged water samples collected from ten different manufacturers from the two mentioned sites (Kebbi State University of Science & Technology and Aliero Onion Market). Sachet water samples (50 sachets per brand) from ten different sources

were filled in 100 ml amounts into sterile plastic bottles and preserved in aseptic conditions as recommended by the standard methods of Greenberg (1992). Samples were refrigerated at 4 °C and analysed within 24h of collection.

Microscopy

Microscopic examinations of the specimens were carried out to check for ova, cysts, worms and trophozoites of protozoa. Ten milliliters (10ml) of each sample was concentrated by centrifugation and a loop of the deposit then viewed under 40X objective of the light microscope.

Estimation and isolation of total coliforms and *E.coli*:

Viable Bacterial Count: Different pathogenic bacteria were enumerated by serial dilution method. One ml aliquots of each dilution (10^{-1} to 10^{-6}) directly inoculated in triplicate on MacConkey Agar, Blood Agar, Nutrient Agar, Eosin Methylene Agar, Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate Agar and Lysine Iron Agar. The culture plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24h. Viable Bacterial count was carried out using colony counter. Statistical analysis was done and data are presented as mean ($n=3$) \pm SD. A single isolated colony was picked up and sub-cultured again on MacConkey agar for the purification of the isolate. Simultaneously, another single colony with similar characters was picked for the preparation of smear and stained with gram stain. Biochemical tests were performed to confirm the *E.coli* using Simmons Citrate Agar, Voges Proskaur, Methyl Red, Catalase test, Urease test etc. (Cruickshank, 1968). Coliforms test was performed to detect coliform bacteria (using *E.coli* as indicator organism) in the water samples according to the method described by Cheesbrough (1991).

Determination of Coliforms

Number of positive test tubes with acid (yellow coloration) and gas production were matched with the McCrady's Statistical Table, and the most probable number (MPN) of coliforms present in 100ml of each sample was thus determined. For the confirmation test, a loopful of cultures from the presumptive test was inoculated into brilliant green broth containing Durham tubes and incubated for 48h at 37 °C. Gas production confirmed the presence of *E.coli*. Cultures were further inoculated into eosin methylene blue medium and incubated at 37 °C for 24h. Purple-green metallic sheen on the surfaces of the colonies indicated a positive test.

RESULTS

Results of Microscopic Examination (Table-1) of the sachet water samples revealed the absence of ova, cysts or trophozoites of protozoa in the test samples.

Results of total viable count or bacteriological analysis of sachet water samples indicated the presence of coliforms or faecal coliforms. The Total Plate Count (TPC) was observed above the specified range (Table-2). Some samples of the ten brands of packaged drinking water showed the growth of *E.coli*. The TPC of the total coliforms or faecal coliforms has been observed in the range of 1200 to 3000 per 100ml. The highest TPC was observed in CS-5 and CS-2 (400) followed by CS-5 (280) and CS-6 (220).

Occurrence of *E.coli* was observed on MacConkey Agar, EMB Agar, Nutrient Agar, Blood Agar and Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate agar and has been identified on the basis of cultural characteristics and biochemical tests as shown in table-3. Significant bacterial counts (cfu/ml) were observed. The results obtained out of 20 samples tested from the two sites, sample CS-1,2,3 and CS-5 showed significant amount of gas production. In EMB Agar, there was also purple metallic sheen on the colonies, thus confirming the presence of *E.coli* in the water samples.

Bacteriological analysis of the sachet water samples from both sites revealed the presence of pathogens including *Streptococcus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Shigella* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *E.coli* and Yeasts (Table-4).

DISCUSSIONS

Bacteriological analysis of the sachet water of common use within the KSUST campus and AOM environment (Table-2) indicates that some of the sachet did not meet the required NAFDAC or WHO standard for potable water. This could be attributed to the bacterial contaminants which could have been introduced during the processing, packaging and distribution stages. The total plate count was observed above the specified range of NAFDAC or WHO or Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON). The data obtained from coliforms count underlines the unsuitability of the brands for human consumption. Ajayi *et al.*, (2008) had reported an earlier study of packaged drinking waters in Ibadan, Nigeria in which larger proportions of sachet water were found to show positive coliforms count compared to bottled waters. According to World Health Organization, 2002 report, a high TPC concentration does not itself present a risk to human health. Nevertheless, HPCs are used as good indicators of the overall quality of production (Ferreira *et al.*, 1994; Obiri-Danso *et al.*, 2003). These may therefore, be used in assessing the cleanliness of the different brands of bottle and sachet drinking waters sold in the selected areas of study.

Results obtained in this study showed that sachet drinking water sold at the two sites in Aliero exhibited variable characteristics in terms of their microbiological quality. According to NAFDAC (2010) *E.coli*, Coliforms and faecal *Streptococci* should be absent in packaged drinking water while results indicates the presence of coliforms group. However, the result of presumptive coliforms test and bacteriological analysis confirms the presence of coliforms (Table-3) in sachet water samples tested. During the bacteriological examination four of the brands revealed the presence of pathogens viz. *Streptococcus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Shigella* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *E.coli* and Yeasts (Table-4). The presence of these contaminating bacteria could account for the incidence of diarrhea, food poisoning, gastroenteritis and typhoid common in the market and university environment, especially, among the students. In bacteriological study of branded bottled waters high total bacterial count was observed, similar findings have been reported by Hunter and Burge (1987) and Fujikawa *et al.*, (1997) in bottled mineral water from Japan. Occurrence of fungal and bacterial foreign contaminant, gram negative and gram positive rods were also reported by them. In 2003, Radhakrishnan *et al.*, have also reported the incidence of *E.coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* and the high viable count than specified by WHO or United Nation's International Childrens Education Fund (UNICEF) or American Public Health Association (APHA) for potable water. Study indicates that bottled water may contaminate prior to bottling or during processing. Packaged waters may present bacterial or viral risks when stored for some length of time in opened containers. Therefore, packaging has to be supervised carefully and any sanitary deficiencies discovered should be corrected immediately (Mossel, 1976).

The presence of pathogenic organisms including bacteria and yeasts in the studied sachet water samples are further indications that the originating source of water is doubtful and this water do not undergo appropriate sterilization techniques. Ground waters such as boreholes when properly constructed and maintained provide a relatively safer source of raw water in terms of microbial load compared to unprotected water sources such as river, spring and well waters (Howard *et al.*, 2003). Ineffectiveness or malfunctioning of the treatment process employed could also result in the presence of coliform bacteria in the samples of water. According to Edberg (1996), no treatment process or method used in mass production of drinking water yields a sterile product; it only produces a safe product devoid of pathogenic organisms. Appropriate treatment processes should, therefore, be utilised for production of quality and safe packaged drinking waters.

In this study, the microbiological analysis of sachet drinking water sold in KSUST and AOM sites revealed the presence of total coliforms and *E. coli* in concentrations that make the products unfit for human consumption going by WHO and NAFDAC recommendations and guidelines. There is, therefore, need for NAFDAC to intensify efforts in the routine monitoring of activities in the packaged drinking water industry. The safety of bottled and sachet drinking water should be ensured through comprehensive regulatory programs at both the federal and state levels. NAFDAC regulations for packaged waters should be protective of public health and there should be continuous adoption of packaged water quality standards. Testing of market samples will be a good way of detecting if the water is actually pure as claimed by these producing companies.

The hunt for quick money has resulted in "pure water" business and the associated inability to follow the specified treatment process. Sachet water, inspite of being sealed, is thus observed to contribute to health risk to

consumers due to the presence of pathogens often associated with food poisoning and intoxication, in the water. Therefore, sachet water business should be critically reviewed by NAFDAC to ensure that producer comply with standards at every stage of production and distribution processes. Defaulters should be banned and fake NAFDAC numbers should be banned. NAFDAC should also organize campaigns to educate producers as well as consumers on the health hazards associated with contaminated or untreated water.

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Table1. Microscopic Examination of the Test Samples for the Presence of any Trophozoa

+/-	Ova	Cysts	Worms	Trophozoites
Sample No.				
CS-1	-	-	-	-
CS-2	-	-	-	-
CS-3	-	-	-	-
CS-4	-	-	-	-
CS-5	-	-	-	-
CS-6	-	-	-	-
CS-7	-	-	-	-
CS-8	-	-	-	-
CS-9	-	-	-	-
CS-10	-	-	-	-

(+) = present; (-) = absent

Table-2: Total Plate Count (TPC) of the Total Coliforms in Different Sachet Water Samples in Comparison to NAFDAC Standards (2010)

S.No.	Sample	TPC (<10cfu/ml)	NAFDAC Standards	
			<i>E.coli</i> (cfu/100ml)	Coliform (cfu/ml)
1	CS-1	160	0	Not>10
2	CS-2	400	0	Not>10
3	CS-3	200	0	Not>10
4	CS-4	400	0	Not>10
5	CS-5	280	0	Not>10
6	CS-6	220	0	Not>10
7	CS-7	196	0	Not>10
8	CS-8	120	0	Not>10
9	CS-9	120	0	Not>10
10	CS-10	170	0	Not>10

Table-3 Cultural Characteristics of *E.coli* on Various Media

	Media Used	Cultural Characteristics
1	MacConkey Agar	Smooth, circular, pink colonies with spreading growth
2	EMB Agar	Flat, deep purple colonies with metallic sheen
3	Nutrient Agar	White, circular, smooth colonies with entire edge
4	Blood Agar	Circular, convex, non-haemolytic colonies with entire edge
5	Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate Agar	Yellow, large, thick and smooth colonies
6	Triple Sugar Iron Agar	No growth
7	Lysine Iron Agar	No growth
	Biochemical Tests	
8	Voges Proskaur	+
9	Methyl Red	+
10	Simmons Citrate Agar	-
11	Catalase	+
12	Urease	-

Where, (+) = positive; (-) = negative

Table-4: Total Bacterial Count of the Pathogens Isolated from Test Samples

S.No.	Isolate	KSUST (log ₁₀ cfu/ml)	AOM (log ₁₀ cfu/ml)
1	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	5.01	5.06
2	<i>Streptococcus</i> species	4.79	4.86
3	<i>Shigella</i> species	3.41	3.31
4	<i>Salmonella</i> species	2.10	2.05
5	<i>Bacillus</i> species	5.12	5.10
6	<i>E.coli</i>	2.0	1.93
7	Yeasts	3.13	4.0

- KSUST = Kebbi State University of Science & Technology
- AOM = Aliero Onion Market

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